

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MILOSI****FIRST NAME: GEORGES NKUWA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ACADEMIC WRITING FEATURES

1) INTRODUCTION

Every academic paper is a kind of communication tool that allows students to convey the acquired knowledge in a certain discipline. Euclid University decide to provide as very first courses “academic writing course” to enable students to become successful upon graduation. For this reason, academic writing and research always feature a serious tone and present particular theories and facts that touch upon a given argument in a particular research field. Writing academically will help EUCLID students analyze, convey understanding, think critically and focus on technique and style as well as improving their learning development.it is serves as a tool of communication that conveys acquired knowledge in a specific field of study.

Writing various types of papers is one of the most dreaded activities which students face in high school and college. It is quite a complicated task at a high level of studies because it includes lengthy procedures of careful research and requires specific skill s depends on Euclid educational format. To encourage students to be better writers, the EUCLID faculty member created writing assignments per period as a part of academic writing course to give students the opportunity to develop good writing skills and to build on the knowledge and feedback from previous material. Law studies demands great precision in the use of language, its interpretation, as well as its vocabulary and I deeply appreciate EUCLID program to remind me basic of academic writing.

2) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM

Basically, plagiarism is passing off someone else's writing as your own. It means taking someone else's words and pretending that they are your own. In its most serious form, it is simply copying someone else's work, word for word, and not acknowledging the source that

they came from. The most important thing is always to quote and reference correctly and then you will avoid problems of plagiarism. Euclid University paid a considerable attention to the use of citation and paraphrasing to avoid plagiarism. (EUCLID 2015, 54-58), The word itself is found in thirteen instances over eight pages that are replete with warnings against the practice along with considerable attention paid to the use of citations and paraphrasing. But if you need to mention someone else's work and you cannot find or don't want to provide a quotation, how can you do it.

a) Citations

Turabian style allows writers to choose from two systems of citing information: Citations are used to give credit to the work or ideas of another author. While direct quotations are useful for impact or precision, it is best to avoid overuse, lest one's work appear unoriginal (EUCLID 2015, 13). The notes and bibliography method allows students will use footnotes or endnotes in the text and a bibliography at the end of the paper. The parenthetical method lets writers use in-text citations (similar to those used Modern Language Association style). Those papers would also include a reference list of works cited at the end.

i) *IN TEXT CITATION*

To begin, a citation is necessary when you have used a direct quotation as well as when you have paraphrased another's work. In Parenthetical Citations-Reference List style, you indicate that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation next to your reference to that source. In-text citations are required when you use someone else's ideas, theories or research in your paper. (EUCLID 2015, 13). The source is cited within the text [or body] of the paper using an author-date citation system, according to APA guidelines.

(1) *Quotation*

When we use quotations from a book or other source, we must also use quotation marks. You must always provide a citation for a quote to show its origin. Also, we must provide a citation for any information that is not common knowledge (EUCLID 2015, 19). If the quotation is over four lines the rules change and the quotation will lose quotation marks, but it will take the place of a paragraph (EUCLID 2015, 24). We must indent the entire quotation and start the quotation on a new line named "block quote" (EUCLID 2015, 70).

Writers within these fields often strive to vary between quoting and paraphrasing, as a text with too many quotations is difficult to read and comes across as too dependent on sources, whereas a text with too much paraphrasing may give the impression of being too superficial. But anyway, we should use quotation when an authority figure says something that can help to persuade the reader (EUCLID 2015, 23). It is also very important apart from quotation marks to use italic to highlight keywords, titles as well as foreign terms.

(2) *Paraphrase*

Writing information in your own words is a highly acceptable way to include the ideas of other people in your writing. It is very important, however, to paraphrase correctly because there is a fine balance between acceptable paraphrasing and unacceptable paraphrasing

(plagiarism). More than ten times the word “*plagiarism*” appears in the course pack, just to let students know that EUCLID devotes particular attention about the issue.

Acceptable paraphrase means to rewrite something ‘in your own words. But should be in author words, in a different style from the original, finally the original works must be cited. Instead, students should paraphrase, restating the ideas in their own words, and in a manner that does not overly resemble the original quotation (EUCLID 2015, 13). A paraphrase may result in a longer, rather than shorter, version of the original text. It offers an alternative to using direct quotations and helps students to integrate evidence/source material into assignments. Paraphrasing is also a useful skill for making notes from readings, note-taking in lectures, and explaining information in tables, charts, and diagrams.

b) LIST OF WORKS CITED

It is necessary to share with the reader that the information included from outside sources originated elsewhere. This is easily done in two ways. In the body of a research project, the student or scholar includes a brief glimpse as to who created the information they have added.

The MLA works cited list is the final page of a research project. Here, the reader can take the time to truly understand the sources included in the body of the project. The reader can turn to the MLA works cited list, If you are referring to an idea from another work but NOT directly quoting the material, or making reference to an entire book, article or other work, you only have to make reference to the author and year of publication and not the page number in your in-text reference. All sources that are cited in the text must appear in the reference list at the end of the paper. The information provided in the reference supplies the reader with enough information to seek out the original source themselves, if he or she would like.

A bibliography is a list of sources that relate to the content in a research paper or project. You can find examples of bibliographies in the final pages of some nonfiction books. Authors sometimes include a list of sources for further or additional reading. This additional reading list is a bibliography.

3) CONCLUSION

Reading there is a significant need for students at all levels not only to be good written communicators, but also to understand the importance of good writing skills. In addition, an important facet of written communication is being able to critically assess the writing of others, particularly at the graduate level as well as in professional programs.

The requirements of scientific writing: objectivity, referencing (separating one’s own and other people’s thoughts and argumentation), focusing on the discussed matter, clear argumentation etc. The idea of an essay is to practice legal writing and using legal sources in one’s texts and the review of grammar and style was useful. As a prosecutor¹, Legal paper writing is the foundation of my career, and it involves endless days and sleepless nights. In order to write a law paper effectively, I need to develop sufficient insight and interest in the legal studies, as well as to be prepared to conduct adequate research. Legal paper writing is

¹ Military public prosecutor in charge of criminal cases and offenses in the army

difficult primarily because developing your own analytical skills needs you to understand preceding perspectives and other scholarly works, this is the challenge that academic writing course purposes to face.

Legal writing and analysis is a type of writing in which we do not only collect data or information coming from other authors but trying to analyse a particular issue, educate, and, in some cases, persuade the reader by delivering his own view on a case. Therefore, by nature, the approach that to take in legal writing is very particular.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.